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SIC Learning Materials Repository integrated in SIC Online Platform and fully developed

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RATIONALE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT

The Learning Materials Repository, represents the SIC Learning Repository that has been developed from M4 until M36 of the project with the overarching aim of supporting all the learning activities developed within SIC.

The SIC Learning Repository has followed a user centred design approach which means that it has been designed and developed on the basis of some fundamental principles as reported in the following:

- 01** The contents of the platform have been developed to correspond to the needs of the SIC networks;
- 02** The Learning Repository has been designed to support activities conducted within WP 3 Experimentation and WP4 Learning; and
- 03** The Learning Repository concept was inspired by the SIC learning principles and and processes developed in D4.1.

Finally, the Learning Repository was required to be: integrated on the SIC platform; open; and continuously updated on the basis of the feedback received from its use in practices.

The rest of this document aims to describe the process of development of the Learning Repository and its coherence with the principles listed above as well as some deviations made in order to include 2 fundamental feedbacks that emerged during the implementation of two main project actions:

- 01** the use of the Learning Repository in long-term experimentation in WP3 and the feedbacks collected in the Policy Master Classes (T5.4) that indicated public sector innovation as one of the less supported areas in terms of learning tools and approaches to develop SI; and
- 02** the development of the SIC sustainability strategy that indicated the Learning Repository as one of the most promising products of the project.

The document is organised in sections: The first one reports the main findings of Deliverable 4.1 on the learning principles for SI, emerging from the main needs of the SIC networks as well as on case studies and literature; section 2 reports the initial concept of the Learning Repository and the functioning prototype delivered to support the first SIC Summer School; section 3 describes the use of the Learning Repository tools in the experimentations conducted in WP3 and in the policy master classes conducted in WP5. The last section describes the Learning Repository's final version and some future activities planned to keep it open for 1 year after the project.

1. COMBINING EXPERIMENTATION AND LEARNING: A FRAMEWORK FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF DESIGN THINKING IN SOCIAL INNOVATION

The SIC learning framework, developed in D4.1, is based on the need clearly expressed by the SIC networks (D4.2) to develop a source of information to make it easier for SI developers, intermediaries and the public sector to design and implement new SI solutions to meet context-based societal challenges.

On this premise, the SIC learning framework was inspired by the idea of introducing design thinking as a means to sustain social innovation as an experiential learning framework.

Social innovation projects are typically small-scale experiments that deal with the development of new services or with the re-design of existing ones. They should thus be interpreted not only as ways of giving shape to innovative services better responding to pressing societal challenges- which is their first objective -, but also as ways of triggering and supporting an interactive and reflective learning.

We thus proposed an experimentation/design thinking cycle, based on Kolb's experiential learning model (Kolb, 1984)¹, the SIC learning framework representing at the same time the core structure of a participatory design processes (which can be complemented with appropriate tools and applied to the co-creation of new services) and of an organisational learning process (which can be complemented with appropriate structures and actions and applied to the introduction and integration of new knowledge). If we interpret the organisation not only as a closed structure, typically represented by a core actor (a municipality, a hospital, a public transportation service provider etc.), but also as a network of actors concurring to the co-design and co-production of the services, the learning process must be regarded as extended to the whole network, and functioning through the aforementioned interactions.

The scheme in figure 1 represents the framework (Rizzo, Deserti & Pous, 2017)² that combines experimenting and learning. It integrates the design thinking methodology (Brown,

¹ Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential Learning: experience as the source of learning and development*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.

² Rizzo, F., Deserti, A. & Pous, M. (2017). *Report on SIC learning principles and processes*, Deliverable 4.1 of the Social Innovation Community EU project, Horizon 2020 programme.

2009)³ in the form of an iterative design process, with Kolb's model of experiential learning: it is based on the idea that design processes can be exploited to set up and pilot experiential learning within organisations. The iterative nature of the design process - based on loops of understanding-designing-and redesigning until the problem is addressed - is complemented with the situated nature of experiential learning, giving way to a "4A" model that starts from the concrete experience of the current situation (**Actual**) and moves to the design of an experimentation (**Act**) by reflecting (**Analyse**), interpreting and envisioning diverse alternatives (**Abstract**). According to the design thinking methodology, the phase of experimentation is supported by the development of prototypes, i.e. design artefacts that represent the concrete implementation of the alternative hypotheses formulated to change the initial situation and that offer the possibility to evaluate their effectiveness, to provide feedback on the hypotheses and to refine the solutions (Manzini & Rizzo, 2011)⁴.

Figure 1. The SIC learning framework based on the design cycle of iterative loops of design-evaluating and re-design and on the Kolb model of reflective learning.

³ Brown, T. (2009). *Change by Design*. New York: HarperCollins.

⁴ Manzini, E. & Rizzo, F. (2011). Small Projects/Large Changes: Participatory Design as an Open Participated Process. *CoDesign: International Journal of CoCreation in Design and the Arts*, 7(3-4): 199-215.

Designing the new solutions and prototyping them in real contexts triggers mechanisms of experiential learning within the whole network of involved actors. In particular, the experimentation loop may provide a substantial contribution to the transformation of internal processes, knowledge and culture of the organisation which is designing the innovation that needs to be changed or developed to effectively deal with the new solutions. By designing new solutions to unmet problems and challenges, an organisation can thus reflect and produce knowledge in a process of continuous learning bound to an experiential learning cycle, including trial-and-error, that is tolerant to failure (at the micro-scale) as a structural feature of the process, is capable of drawing resources from the contexts in which problems arise and is based on engagement with potential users as co-designers, evaluators of the alternatives and even co-producers.

On the basis of this learning model, the design of the Learning Repository was organised in order to develop a tool to support the users along the 4 phases of the learning/design cycle:

- Context analysis;
- Reframing problems;
- Envisioning alternatives; and
- Prototyping.

In addition to these core areas the manual contains also additional areas devoted to: advertise/disseminate about a project; launch a call for project; prepare a project proposal for a pitch; evaluate the project sustainability.

2. THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE SIC LEARNING REPOSITORY

The design process of the Learning Repository was based on the following phases:

- 01** User profiles;
- 02** Information architecture;
- 03** Content development;
- 04** Functioning prototype;
- 05** Testing and feedback collection; and
- 06** Release of the final version.

User profiles

The selection of the most relevant user profiles was conducted together with all of the SIC partners and special attention was devoted to understand - with the help of the 8 SIC

Networks, 11 from August 2017, - the main actors that populated their different networks. The consortium individualised 3 main profiles for the Learning Repository:

Intermediaries

Mediator/facilitator of the learning process working with different target groups or facilitating cross-sector and/or cross-thematic groups with the goal of raising their capacity in the area of social innovation and leaving them with tools to continue implementing the process of social innovation on their own.

Public/Private sectors

Public government agencies, local, regional and national governments, public institutions and private sector actors with a commitment to supporting social change, e.g. non-profit organisations, charities, co-operatives and social enterprises. They will most likely need a facilitator/intermediary to support the process.

Innovators

This could be an individual, a team, a local community (represented by an individual and/or a team) that would like to embark on this process on its own or use a facilitator. They are likely to select the tools that best suit their context.

On the basis of these profiles, the mission of the Learning Repository was defined:

The SIC Learning Repository is an online, open resource available for innovators, intermediaries and public sector/private sectors to improve their skills in design for Social Innovation.

Technological solution

The Learning Repository was developed on Wordpress CMS in order to allow for the aesthetic adaptation of the system to the graphic identity relative to the parent site.

The graphic customization and page-layouting are managed by a commercial framework (UNCODE) that allows for total control of the aesthetic and content positioning.

From the navigation/usability point of view, the website provides dual usability of the whole platform structured on two levels: an informational and an instrumental one.

Both levels of usability contain articles extended on different media including also downloadable documents in PDF format.

The peculiar feature of the Wordpress CMS together with the powerful graphic framework

Uncode simplify updating and adding content to the site even for less experienced users. The site is currently hosted by the platform VHosting Solution S.r.l. (vhosting.it) under a shared Linux server system.

URL: www.silearning.eu

The discussion on the interaction between the SIC website and the SIC Learning Repository started at the kick-off meeting of the project in 2016, when all the partners discussed the architecture of the SIC platform/s.

The choice was between having independent online platforms that linked each other or to have the Learning Repository as a nested page of the SIC platform.

The Learning Repository has been described in the DoA as a nested page of the project platform from which to retrieve some articles, case studies, and other materials to better understand what social innovation is.

However, the information coming from the networks' learning needs (D4.2) indicated a different concept for the Learning Repository which was more interactive and larger than what was envisioned at the beginning.

Furthermore, the discussion surrounding the SIC sustainability strategy had pushed since the beginning the attention of the project to develop “products” that could be independent from the main SIC project platform, whose sustainability was not guaranteed after the end of the project.

For these reasons, the final decision was to develop the Learning Repository as an independent website (URL: <http://www.silearning.eu/>) to be linked to the SIC website so that if practices and uses would have demonstrated the value of the Learning Repository its maintenance would then be easier.

Resources

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SIC has produced a lot of useful tools and experiences to pass on. We have developed a **Learning Repository** - as an online handbook, open resource available for innovators, researchers and policy makers to improve their skills in design for Social Innovation.

Figure 2. A screen shot of the SIC website (<https://www.siceurope.eu/resources>) that shows the availability of the link to the Learning Repository

Information architecture

The SIC Learning Repository's first prototype was organised around the following areas of contents:

- 01** the handbook of social innovation in which learning materials and tools can be found on how to develop social innovation;
- 02** the collection of tools used during the SIC experimentation mentioned above; a list of resources outside the SIC world, useful to further support learning on social innovation; and
- 03** the collection of SIC case studies on social innovation, which was developed to understand the process of learning at work in different contexts.

Figure 3. The content areas of the SIC Learning Repository

Content development

Handbook

This is the largest area of the Learning Repository. It is organised in 8 areas of activities:

Figure 4. The areas of activity of the SIC Learning Repository Handbook

The chapters of the handbook cover all the activities that can be included in the SIC learning framework. A user can plan a process of SI design (as in Figure 1) by selecting an area of activity, studying it and proceeding through the different modules to select the necessary tools to perform the design process.

Each area of activity includes an introduction and a series of modules:

IDEATION

In the Ideation phase, innovators will frame the social problem and define their customer/user/beneficiary. It is an exciting phase, in which discovery research meets the first moment of convergence, transforming into ideas.

In ideation, innovators will learn how to use tools that help frame the problem at hand by looking deep into the many underlying factors. Once the problem has been explored and fine-tuned into a precise challenge, innovators can advance into the idea generation module, in which, innovators will learn brainstorming techniques and how to come up with ideas to solve the problem through the aid of specific tools. Once a healthy amount of tangible ideas has been produced, specific tools will be offered to help select the most viable ones to be promoted to the development phase.

What you'll walk away with after taking the modules:

- 01** A clearly defined challenge to a specific and honed social problem to benefit a precise target(s)
- 02** A vast array of possible ideas to tackle the problem
- 03** A small selection of viable ideas to prototype

MODULES

- PROBLEM FRAMING**
- IDEA GENERATION**
- IDEA SCREENING**

Figure 5. The ideation chapter in the Learning Handbook

Modules contain a series of tools that support the users to perform the activity, as shown in Figure 6:

PROBLEM FRAMING Home / modules / Problem Framing

What will you find here?

This learning module will give you an overview of tools to help you define the social problem at its core. While quite typically, social innovators know the problem quite well – whether they are directly affected by it or have a close but indirect connection to it, exploring the problem beyond the initial lens is essential towards finding effective solutions. The tools provided will in fact encourage the innovator to reframe the problem to better fit the challenge and the desired impact.

What will you learn?

Through this module you will learn how to define the problem by taking a look at not only the immediate circle of stakeholders affected by the problem but the surrounding context as well (e.g. cultural and political factors, macro-economic conditions, market analysis etc.). Once the condition-setting factors have been fully investigated, attention will be placed on the final users/beneficiaries and paying customers through an immersive analysis. Finally, a check will be performed to test whether or not the newly, reframed social challenge is ready to be tackled.

TOOLS

- TARGET GROUP**
teamwork session
1 hour
- PERSONAS**
teamwork session
2 hours
- THINKING HATS**
teamwork session
1-2 hours
- PROBLEM DEFINITION**
teamwork session
1-2 hours
- CHECKING YOUR CHALLENGE**
teamwork session
4-5 hours

Figure 6. The module with all the related tools

Tools can be selected, downloaded and used to perform a specific task. For example, the tool “personas” supports the users conducting SI activities to better understand the people who

are experiencing the problem, i.e. the future end-user of a new social innovation solution (see annex 1).

Tools

In this section, tools developed during the SIC experimentation with the five SIC host centers are presented (<https://www.siceurope.eu/countries/spain/final-event-review-more-experimentation-please>). The tools are organised according to the main activities/actions that can support the development of a social innovation. Specifically, they are organised around the 7 categories of the handbook.

Resources

This section contains links and references (projects, toolkits, articles and other materials) to online resources produced by other actors than SIC but which can be useful for SI actors and decision makers to learn more on the following: SI processes, solutions, and best practices. These external resources have been selected by SIC partners, as they are complementing the projects own learning offers, and there would be no need to replicate. This section will be continuously updated, thanks to the work of SIC partners who will scout, analyse and publish new contents relevant for social innovation.

Figure 7. The external resources available on the SIC Learning Repository

Cases

This area contains a series of 12 case studies that have been developed by SIC partners on success stories in implementing SI. The cases are built from the perspective of the design cycle process and the reader can learn the main phases of the design process that characterised each experience.

The cases are presented with a short abstract. The complete version can be downloaded in pdf.

Figure 8. The area of the SIC case studies

3. THE EXPERIMENTATION PROCESS OF THE SIC LEARNING REPOSITORY

The SIC Learning Repository was experimented in 2 different real contexts:

- 01** The SIC training activities: summer schools, workshop/relays, policy master classes; and
- 02** The SIC experimentations: 5 host centers dealing with the process of designing a new social innovation solution for a specific societal challenge in different cultural

and territorial contexts.

The content of the Learning Repository has been used by experts in co-design and social innovation to design specific training pathways.

The test of the SIC Handbook and the tools had a long duration: it started with the first summer school held in September 2016 and finished with the last summer school held in Budapest in September 2018.

The testing has been conducted on both:

- The usability of the learning tools; and
- The usability of the Learning Repository website.

The testing on the tools was conducted in the summer schools (T4.3), the relays workshops (T4.4), and the policy master classes (T5.4).

The summer schools were designed as 3,5 days courses. Participants were involved in morning sessions with case study presentations and lectures and in afternoon co-design workshops. In each of the 5 summer schools, three workshops were conducted during which participants were trained to move along 3 phases:

- Context analysis;
- Problem reframe; and
- Envisioning alternatives.

These three phases (that correspond to 3 of the 4 phases of the SIC learning framework) have been conducted thanks to the use of specific tools selected from the Learning Repository.

Also the relays workshops (T4.4) were conducted as co-design activities during which participants started by analysing a specific problem and ended with a social innovation idea to solve it.

The policy master classes were designed in a different format and with different aims. In the policy master class, the participants – policy makers – were involved to learn about co-design and how it can effectively support policy making.

In all three learning situations (policy master classes, summer schools and learning relays), the contents of the Learning Repository were designed and selected by experts in design

thinking and social innovation, and used by non-experts in design thinking and unusual suspect in Social Innovation.

Collected Feedbacks from the learning activities

Feedbacks of the attendees to the SIC learning activities have been collected using questionnaires at the end of each learning activities. Feedbacks of the experts have been collected as free comments.

Feedbacks from the experts have focused the meta-information on each of the used tools and they can be synthesized as follows:

- 01** Instructions on how to use them are clear and effective;
- 02** the graphic style is enjoyable and the fact that they can be printed from the website in 2 different size (A4 and A3) supports experts to use them in different activities involving different numbers of attendees;
- 03** there is a lack in terms of instructions on how to compose the different tools with respect to the learning experience they can support.

Feedbacks from the trainees have focused more the usability of the tools and they can be synthesized as follows:

- 01** the instructions were clear and the tools were clearly organised and effectively designed to guide people into their use even without a trainer;
- 02** instructions that guide the users to fill in the tools are clear but sometime sit can be difficult to use them without a tutor (especially when it is the first time for a user to interact with a tool);

Both groups of users (experts and non-experts) commented on the website, stating that they would like to have not only the tools organised in learning areas but also examples of activities based on their use.

Another relevant feedback is the need for a better explanation of the different areas of the different sections composing the website information architecture. Specifically, the section on Tools has been noticed as an issue of feedback since it contains the same tools that are presented in the handbook. This was however the purpose of the designer, who designed the Tools section separately to provide an easy and quick access to the SI tools in the interest of supporting experts in easily retrieving specific tools instead of going through all the learning areas of the handbook. However, novices disagreed with section but the experts agreed to

keep it also in the second version of Learning Repository.

Collected Feedbacks from the experimentation activities

With respect to the experimentation activities conducted under WP3, the number of used tools was larger than that used in training activities and it included tools coming from all learning areas of the handbook.

Attendees of the experimentation activities expressed 2 main needs with respect to the Learning Repository:

- 01** The need of having examples of use of the tools for specific activities; and
- 02** The need of having specific contents and learning materials for the public sector user profile.

This second feedback seems to directly depend on the fact that different leaning repositories and toolkits are available today for intermediaries⁵ but none of this is specifically devoted to support the introduction of design thinking and social innovation in the public sector.

4. THE LEARNING REPOSITORY'S FINAL VERSION

The final version of the Learning Repository took into account and integrated all of the feedbacks on the tools of the SIC handbook the collected during the training and the experimentation activities⁶.

In the period from December 2018 to end of January 2019, the development of the new version of the Learning Repository has been conducted together with 2 usability testing session during which potential users (selected in the Municipality of Turin, one of the SIC host center, see WP3) have been testing its usability and effectiveness.

⁵ This was not the situation when SIC started.

⁶ The development of the final version of the Learning Repository has been possible thanks to a coral decision of all the SIC consortium that decided to support this second development by allowing the budget not used by ZSI for developing the research portal to this objective. UNIBO, as the partner responsible for the Learning Repository, decided to engage a designer to accomplish the technical aspect of this task. UNIBO allotted an extra effort on the curation of the contents of the Learning Repository for 1 year after the end of the project.

In particular, the current version of the Learning Repository is composed of 2 main areas:

- 01** a landing page as a blog devoted to one of the three main users' profiles: the public sector;
- 02** the SIC handbook for Social Innovation, named social innovation manual, as it was already presented in the first version of the Learning Repository and enriched with learning paths modelled starting from the learning activities conducted under WP4 Learning.

Figure 9. The home page of the Learning Repository (second release)

The landing page of the Learning Repository is a blog for the public sector where users can find different learning materials produced during the SIC project on how to introduce co-design and social innovation in the public sector.

The development of a blog specifically devoted to public sector answers to one of the main feedbacks received during the development of the experimentation and learning activities that pointed out the lack of an on line source for public sector where to find information and retrieve knowledge on the introduction of social Innovation as a new paradigm for public services innovation. The public sector blog also collects all the resources and the case studies already in use in the first version of the Learning Repository and the case studies produced by SIC partners to tell the stories of the 5 experimentations conducted under WP3 as they are complex cases where public sector is involved as the leader of the SI experimentation or as one of the main stakeholder involved in the experimentation process.

Public Sector Innovation Blog

The SIC Public Sector Innovation Blog is an online, open resource available for civil servants, policy makers, practitioners and researchers to expand their knowledge on how to manage co-creation in the public sector.

SOCIAL INNOVATION MANUAL

READ MORE

The Lisbon Social Innovation Declaration
January 29, 2018

EU policymakers are negotiating Europe's next long-term budget and the EU Declaration today to set them. But Europe needs innovation to benefit everyone.

READ MORE

Introducing Design culture in Social Innovation and in the Public Sector
January 24, 2018

The 26 November 2018 POLIN (POLIN) ran the first workshop on the issue of how to use design competences and methodology in public sector and in social innovation.

The workshop started from the consideration that the economic, demographic, social, and environmental long-term challenges are calling for deep changes, questioning many of the assumptions that have underpinned public services and posing new challenges for institutions, policy makers, civil servants, and communities. While working measures are being adopted, innovative solutions based on the active involvement and engagement of citizens emerge as a new paradigm, questioning the established welfare systems and making quite a few unvisited problems.

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Spreading social innovation to where it is needed most
Julie Murk

Regional empowerment and peer learning enabled by the SIC summer school

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Presentation of the Turin experimentation at the Sev Des international conference 2018
January 24, 2018

The last 21st of June the SIC experimentation conducted within the Municipality of Turin has been presented within the Sev Des international conference.

The experimentation took place from November 2016 until June 2018 and it represents original steps of introducing social innovation in public sector as a new paradigm to deal with the challenge of how to provide public sector offering.

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Logos of partner organizations: nestlé, ALMA MATER UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA, Università del Piemonte Orientale, TEKNOLOGISK INSTITUT, drift for transition, THE YOUNG FOUNDATION, tu technische universität düsseldorf, aeidl, social innovation lab, REVES, ZSI, six.

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Figure 10. The blog for the public sector

The second area of content of the Learning Repository is the SIC handbook (developed under WP3 Experimentation, T 3.6) re-named “social innovation manual”.

With respect to the first version of the Learning Repository, the manual has been complemented with 4 learning paths.

The learning paths are models of learning activities, designed from the learning activities conducted in SIC that can be used by anyone to implement:

- 01** Co-design project;
- 02** Summer school;
- 03** relays workshop; and
- 04** Policy master classes.

Below, a view of the section Social Innovation manual (fig. 11) and a view of the summer school learning path where users can find an explanation of what the summer school is and instructions on how to implement it with related tools. The tools support the co-design of a social innovation solution and are part of the larger collection of the tools developed for the social innovation manual.

ASSESSING REPOSITORY PUBLIC SECTOR INNOVATION BLOG SOCIAL INNOVATION MANUAL TOOLS

PUBLIC SECTOR INNOVATION BLOG SOCIAL INNOVATION MANUAL

LEARNING PATH OF: SUMMER SCHOOL →

The Social Innovation Manual is an online, open resource available for innovators, intermediaries and public sector/private sectors to improve their skills in design for Social Innovation.

READ MORE →

Intermediaries
Mediator/facilitator of the learning process that works with different target groups or facilitates the cross-sector and/or cross-thematic groups with a goal to raise their capacity in the area of social innovation and leaves them with tools to continue implementing the process of social innovation on their own.

Public/Private sectors
Public government agencies, local, regional and national governments, public institutions and private sector actors with a commitment to supporting social change like non-profit organisations, charities, co-operatives and social enterprises. They will most likely need a facilitator/intermediary to support the process.

Innovators
this could be an individual, a team, a local community (represented by an individual and/or a team) that would like to embark on this process on its own or use a facilitator. They are likely to select the tools that best suit their context.

RECRUITING SOCIAL INNOVATORS >
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Figure 11. The social innovation manual

learning path 01: SUMMER SCHOOL

What is the SIC Summer School

The SIC Summer School is a learning event whose aim is to support participants to acquire skills and knowledge on how to design a SI solution that address specific local challenges/place based challenges.

SIC summer school is open to a mix of attendees both in terms of back-ground and role practitioners, students, researchers, stakeholders and problems owners local authorities work all together by applying co-design methodology and tools.

The SIC summer school usually run along 3 days and half and it is based on a mix of lectures and case studies in the morning and co-design workshops in the afternoons.

The SIC summer school can be organized by any of the local stakeholders that share an interest in a place based challenge.

The notion of place based challenge can be referred to a territory like a city, a region, and rural area or even a smaller context like a neighborhood, a street.

The SIC summer school can be also applied to a place which is intangible like an organization.

Common characteristics of all these contexts are: the presence of a community that would benefit from solving a specific challenge it is affected by and the context dependency of the challenge per se that call for an bottom-up and participatory approach.

[download presentation pdf](#)

Related tools:

BUSINESS MODEL teamwork session 2 hours	CUSTOMER JOURNEY teamwork session 2 hours	IDEA CARD teamwork session 2-3 hours	PERSONAS teamwork session 2 hours
PROBLEM DEFINITION teamwork session 1-2 hours	STAKEHOLDERS MAP teamwork session 3 hours		

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Figure 12. The Summer school path: instructions to implement it and related tools

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STEPS

The Learning Repository has been identified as one of the most valuable SIC products. It has successfully been used to support many of the SIC interactive activities and has been communicated and disseminated across different events, always receiving very positive comments.

The new focus of the Learning Repository on the learning needs of the public sector seems to be a strategic and promising trajectory for its sustainability after the project. In this regard, SIC partners have agreed, under the leadership of WP4 lead UNIBO/POLIMI, to keep the Learning Repository active after the SIC H2020 projects comes to an end in February 2019, and feed it with new contents to further disseminate SI in public organisations. Specifically, SIC partners commit themselves to continuously disseminate the Learning Repository towards public sector, to use the Learning Repository every time when they work in public sector and in Social Innovation projects, to update the Learning Repository with open contents on the topic of introducing Social Innovation in Public sector.

Specifically, the Learning Repository will be:

- Open and managed for 1 year after the end of the project by UNIBO/POLIMI;
- Fed with content like news, new tools, new models of activities and new case studies by all the SIC partners who have already committed themselves to this task (see the final sustainability strategy of the project); and
- Available to be used in other projects where SIC partners will be involved in the future. In these cases the Learning Repository as an open source will be available for other projects that are committed to update the Learning Repository with new and open contents.

The Learning Repository will be disseminated continuously in all the SI actions and activities UNIBO/POLIMI will be involved in.

Partners in SIC will be asked to disseminate it through their official digital channels as well as to include it in all the actions/initiatives they will carry on related to SI.

The Learning Repository will be the basis of all the training activities conducted by ESSI (the European School of Social Innovation, <https://www.essi-net.eu>). In particular, the SIC Learning Repository will be used in the future summer schools ESSI will organise/co-produce with its network and beyond.

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

ANNEX 1: The tool personas to describe end users of a Social Innovation solution

**SOCIAL
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TOOL TEMPLATE: PERSONAS

References: Nesta's DIY Toolkit

Who are your beneficiaries, customers and financing supporters?

Complexity: Low
Time required: 2 hours
Material required: pen

What is it for?

Personas are fictional characters who embody the archetype of your customer, beneficiary or financing supporter. They are created through exhaustive observation of the customer segment and the drawing together of their shared characteristics, behaviors, motivations, interests, etc. It is a useful tool to really focus on getting to know who you are designing for.

How to use it?

The goal of the activity is to make the persona as accurate as possible and hence as detailed and nuanced as can be. Start by giving your persona a name and identifying from which customer segment s/he comes from. Then move on to describing who s/he is: age, personal background, education level, profession, etc. Now, make a sketch of your persona (remember you can always take a picture and use photo to sketch technology if you can't draw). Move on to the other sections in any order you'd like and feel free to add more details!

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Persona Name:

Customer Segment:

Who am I?

**3 Reasons for me
to engage with you:**

**3 Reasons for me
not to engage with you:**

My Interests

My Personality

My Skills

My Dreams

**My Social
Environment**